

TRANSFORMATION OF VARIETIES OF ENGLISH IN THE PEDAGOGICAL DISCIPLINE

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Abstract. *Learning society is a condition of human survival. To know foreign language, its history, borrowings, variants, dialects, accents means an extension of human identity, new possibilities to communicate with people from different nations.*

Keywords: *accent, dialects, essence, variant, regional, social, phonemic, phonetic, language*

The English language has become the global language, the language essential in promoting cultural relations, in the areas of air traffic control, transportation, tourism, study and work abroad, international business, scientific conferences and research, entertainment, politics, literature, history and religion.

That is why so important to know the essence and fortune of social and regional dialects and accents of contemporary Great Britain. What are the peculiarities of the dialects of Cornwall, Yorkshire, Lancashire ? How can you understand a phrase in Cockney?

How do people implement the rhyming slang of East London, which is considered to be unique? How many groups of regional dialects are there in Great Britain? What can we do in order to save and hand down these unique variants of English to the next generations?

The proposed research will give us possible answers, considering the essence of the dialect together with the history of the region where it is used.

The **Problem** of the research is the fate of social and regional dialects of contemporary Great Britain.

The **Aim** of the research is to investigate the dialects and accents of contemporary Great Britain which are in danger of disappearance from the face of the Earth.

The **Method** of the research is the theoretical analysis of the linguistic, pedagogical and psychological literature on the topic.

I. Regional Variants of the English Language in Great Britain

Since the days of Shakespeare the English language of South East England was considered as the *standard*. According to Arnold (1996), *Standard English* is the official language of Great Britain, taught at schools and universities, used by press, radio, TV, spoken by the educated people. This English language is current and literary. Its vocabulary is contrasted to various local dialects.

The author should clarify two terms – “a dialect”, and “an accent”.

One uses the term “a dialect” to refer to varieties distinguished from each other by the differences of grammar and vocabulary, whereas “an accent” will refer to the varieties of pronunciation (Hughes, 1994):

“Dialect” – a manner of speaking; phraseology; idiom; a form of a language prevailing in a particular district, and marked by peculiarities of vocabulary or pronunciation; a special variety or branch of language, or one of a number of languages regarded as a family; a form of a language characteristic of a particular profession or trade, whereas “accent” – a special effort of utterance

making one syllable more prominent than others, as by a change of pitch or by stress of voice; manner of utterance (Finnegan, 1989).

Scottish, Welsh and Irish are generally the most popular regional accents, then Northern, Yorkshire and West Country accents come, and at the bottom of the list there are London's, Liverpool's, Glasgow's and West Midlands', the least popular accents in Great Britain. Regional varieties possessing a literary form are called "variants" (Arnold, 1996).

There are two variants in contemporary Great Britain:

- Scottish English, and
- Irish English (Hughes, 1994)

Opinions on the number of main groups of dialects vary.

They are distinguished from each other by the absence of Long Mid Diphthong in the western south-west part of Great Britain. East Anglia has preserved initial [h], both East Anglia and the south part of Midlands have completed [j]-dropping.

Within the southern area, two south-west areas are distinguished by having [r] in "bar" and "bark". Non-prevocalic [r] is preserved in central Lancashire. Such words like "money" have final [i] in the North-East, Humberside, Merseyside, and West Midlands areas. Long Mid Diphthonging in the words "gate" and "coat" occurs in Merseyside, in the North-West, East, Western parts of Midlands. The author notes that the word "dialect" is used in two meanings nowadays, to denote:

- old dialects which are becoming extinct now,
- regional variants, i.e. a literary standard with some features from local dialects.

The most marked difference among dialects and regional variants lies in the fact that dialects possess phonemic distinctions, whereas regional variants are characterized by phonetic distinctions (Arnold, 1994).

Even among the educated the speech of Northern England differs considerably from that of the South. The southern vowel [ʌ] occurs in the North as [u] in such words as "butter", "cut", "guy", and some southern vowels, the southern retracted vowel [a:] occurs as the short vowel [a] in the northern dialects, for example, in the words "chaff", "grass", "path". Seventeen different vowels occur in the word "house", including the vowel [u:] of the Old English word "hus", at least in the six northern counties. Let us analyze some dialects, variants and accents more in detail.

II. Cornwall and Cornish

Now let's go to mystic Cornwall in order to get to know Cornish...

"Cornwall"- means "Cornubian Welsh"; the name Wealhas

(Wales, Welsh) was a common noun, meaning "strangers"; it was given by the newcomers to the unfamiliar Celtic tribes...

But how can one get here, in Cornwall, Somerset? The gentle landscape of Somerset is a home to the Somerset cider, or "Scrumpy", - an alcoholic apple drink- and cheese. Cider is made from apples only and is sold all over the United Kingdom, but "Scrumpy" is much stronger, and it usually has small pieces of fruit floating in it. "Cheddar" cheese, the most popular and firm cheese, was stored and matured in caves at Cheddar Gorge.

Cornwall is famous for its distinct culture as it was settled by Celts from Brittany and Ireland. Cornwall is mystic, Celtic and historical. The Lizard, the southern part of England, took its name from the Cornish "lit", palace and yard, appropriate words for this majestically beautiful coast.

According to The Oxford Companion to the English Language (1992);

Cornwall – [before 10 c; from Old English Cornweallas
- the “Cornwelsh Celtic equivalents Kerno’u or Pou Kerno’u
(Latin pagus Cornubii, medieval Latin Cornubia).

Compare the district of Cornwaille in Britany, known in Breton as Kernēo’ and Kerne’.

Some words derived the name from Celtic “corn (u) horn “, for the shape of the peninsula. Official title is - Cornwall and Isles of Scilly. A county of England occupying the extreme south-western peninsula]. Cornwall is considered the most remote English dialect of the counties of England, romantically associated with tin mining, megaliths, smugglers and wreckers. Although the region was a part of England since 815, many local people regard England as situated beyond the River Tamar. The people of Cornwall were always proud of their language. The efforts are being made to revive it now. The old language survives chiefly in the form of place-names, folk dances and folk music festivals, for example, celebrations of the May Day derived from old fertility rites, the unique form of wrestling.

The May Day is celebrated as a spring festival, this tradition came from the ancient times. The English and other people conquered by the Romans developed their May Day from the Roman festival called “Floralia”. The May Day became the most favourite holiday of many English villagers from the medieval times. Although the Cornish language ebbed away over the centuries it is still recalled in the Celtic place-names, as it was mentioned above.

According to the Oxford Companion to the English language (1992: 265);

Cornish – [16c: from Corn(wall) and – ish : Celtic equivalents Kerniak, Kernewek, the ancient Celtic language of Cornwall].

” In Cornwall is two speches; the one is naughty Englyshe, and the other is Cornyshe speche’ (Boorde, 1547).

The information about the early Cornish “scant” we can find in few texts, the major survivor was ” The Ordinalia ”, (written, probably, in the late 14century), a trilogy of verse dramas of 8734 lines in all.

The Cornish language began to decline from the time of Reformation. Relics of the Cornish language are found in places and family names beginning with

- “pen” head, hill (Pendennis, Penhale, Penzance),
- “pol” pool, hole (Polkerris, Polmassick, Polperro),
- “porth” port (Porthallow, Pothcothan, Portcurno),
- “tre” farm (Tremaim, Tresillian, Trevelyan).

Cornwall has St. Michael’s Mount, while Britany has Mont-Saint-Miche. Both have many Celtic saints’ names, and the characteristic features of Cornwall is the existence of names of many saints: St. Austell, St. Buryan, St. Columb, St. Ewe, St. Ives, St. Just, St. Levan, St. Mawgan, St. Newlyn.

The change of speech could formerly be heard at the country boundary, but Devon speech encroached upon the north-west about the River Bude. The guttural usage of Devon is weakened in Cornwall, but not so much as formerly. The dialect used in Cornwall is a part of the West Country group, but because Cornish survived so long, the local variant of English was developed as a language learned from foreigners, leading to many differences from the speech of Devon. In the dialect there are words wholly or partly derived from Cornish, such as:

“clicky-handed”- left-handed (from glikin), “ clunk” to swallow, and “whidden” runt or weakling (in a litter of piglets; from “gwyn” white).

Revived Cornish exists now as well. It is partly artificial language administered by Kesva Tavas Kernevek – The Cornish Language Board, set up in 1967 to promote the study and revival of the Cornish language. This medium is sometimes referred to scholars as “Pseudo-Cornish “, and, according to Price (1984) is called “Cornic”.

The revival began with the appearance of the book

“ A Handbook of the Cornish Language” (1904) by the Cornish nationalist Henry Jenner, followed by Robert Morton Nance’s “Cornish for All”; “A Guide to Unified Cornish” (St. Ives, 1929), Nance’s dictionaries published by the Federation of Old Cornwall Societies, and A.S.D. Smith’s Grammar “Cornish Simplified” (1939). The revivalists claim that the traditional English accent in Cornwall provides a key to Cornish pronunciation.

III. The Scousers and Their Accent

Have you ever heard about “Scouse” ? Let’s come to the native land of the legendary “Beatles” - to Liverpool. Liverpool is best known among the popular music lovers of all over world, especially in the 1960s when the “Beatles” started there...

According to Oxford Companion to the English Language (1992:910);

Scouse [From 18c. lobscouse, a sailor’s dish of stewed meat, vegetables, and ship’s biscuit, not unlike Irish stew. “ Lobscouser “ was a slang name for a sailor.

The terms “Scouse” and “ Scouser” for someone from Liverpool seem to be recent, and probably arose because the city was a port and stew was a feature of the diet, the OED cites the “Southern Daily Echo” (1945), in which “ a scouse” is explained as “ a native of Liverpool where they eat “ scouse ”].

1. Also Scouser. A person born in the city of Liverpool, on the River Mersey, especially if from working class.

2. The often stigmatized working class speech of Merseyside.

The accent combines the features of Lancashire with varieties of English from Ireland and to a lesser extent from Wales, brought in by 19-20 century immigration.

Accents range from broad Scouse through modifications towards RP and RP itself in the middle and upper classes. Among the distinctive expressions in Scouse are “the Pool”, a nickname for Liverpool, and Liverpoolian (the correct name for someone born in Liverpool, substituting “puddle” for “ pool ”). Non-Scousers, especially from the north of the city, are sometimes called “woolybacks” (sheep), a nickname suggesting rusticity and lack of wits.

Conclusion. Dialects, accents and variants of English are the essential components of the history of the language, culture and history of Great Britain. Helping people to achieve intercultural sensitivity, establishing a willingness to understand, creating an open-minded attitude towards their own and the target cultures through implementing the language and its variants, in all these ways foreign language teaching can contribute to the students’ personal growth, development and life-long intercultural learning and communication.

We should study and save all variants of the English language of contemporary Great Britain and successfully implement them nowadays.

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